

ABSTRACT

This descriptive-correlational research was conducted to determine teachers' problems and issues in teaching mother tongue-based multilingual education and pupils' academic performance in the District of Dingle. The entire population of Grade two Elementary teachers representing the different schools and sections in the whole District of Dingle was the respondents of this study. The descriptive statistical tools employed were the mean and the standard deviation, and for the inferential statistics, the Kruskal-Wallis test, the Mann-Whitney test, and Spearman's rho were used. The findings revealed that as an entire group, the problem and issues in teaching mother tongue-based multilingual education of the respondents were severe. When they were classified to age, length of teaching experience, teaching position, and educational attainment, they also exhibited severe problems and issues in teaching mother tongue-based multilingual education; as a whole, in the categories of age, length of teaching experience, teaching position and bachelor's degree with MA units categorized in educational attainment, their pupils have approaching proficiency academic performance; however, those who are bachelors' degree with masters' degree their pupils have developing academic performance; there is no significant difference in the levels of the problems and issues encountered by the respondents when classified as to age, length of teaching experience, teaching position and educational attainment; there is no significant difference in the academic performance of the respondents when classified as to age, length of teaching experience, teaching position and educational attainment. Finally, there is no significant relationship between the problems and issues encountered by the respondents and the academic performance of the respondents' pupils.

Keywords: *Problems, Issues in Teaching, Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education, Academic Performance*

INTRODUCTION

The linguistic and cultural diversity in the Philippines brings much complexity to the issue of language policy in education (Burton, 2013). With more than 7000 islands and 181 distinct languages, the Philippines offers a challenging environment for implementing a language policy that can serve the whole country. Consequently, language policies for Philippine schools have fluctuated dramatically over the last century, with a different policy for nearly every generation. Until recently, the 1974 and 1987 Bilingual Education Policies determined the language of instruction in schools to be Filipino and English. This is even though about 80% of the population does not speak either as a first language (Lewis et al., 2013).

In 2009, the Department of Education (DepEd) challenged the Bilingual Education Policy by issuing an order that called for the institutionalization of mother tongue-based multilingual education (MTB-MLE).

The Department of Education (2009) issued a memorandum order that requires the use of the learners' first language as the medium of instruction for all subject areas in pre-kindergarten through grade three, with Filipino and English being taught as separate subjects. This order focused on the speed in which students will gain literacy skills under the MTB-MLE reform: learners learn to read more quickly when in their first language (L1); pupils who have learned to read and write in their first language learn to speak, read, and write in a second language (L2) and third language (L3) more quickly than those who are taught in a second or third language first; and in terms of cognitive development and its effects on other academic areas, pupils taught to read and write in their first language acquire such competencies more quickly.

Another order was issued in 2012 that offered more specific guidelines for mother tongue-based multilingual education and embedded the reform in the newly adopted K to 12 Basic Education Program (DepEd, 2012). This order shifted from the original mother tongue approach by specifying twelve major regional languages to be used as the languages of instruction. Under this order, teachers are provided government-issued materials in their regional languages but are expected to adapt them to reflect the student's first languages. Furthermore, this order included objectives that more broadly emphasized the influence of MTB-MLE on four areas of development: language development which establishes a vital education for success in school and for lifelong learning; cognitive development, which focuses on Higher Order Thinking Skills (HOTS); Academic development which prepares the learner to acquire mastery of competencies in each of the learning areas; and socio-cultural awareness which enhances the pride of the learner's heritage, language and culture.

According to Ramirez et al. (1991) and Thomas and Collier (1997), the move by DepEd and Congress to adopt MTB-MLE was based on the outcomes of previous quantitative, longitudinal studies that highlighted the benefits of using the mother tongue as the language of instruction.

Walter and Dekker (2011) concluded that minority language students who gained literacy in their first language experienced higher academic achievement than students who learned in a second or third language. These findings are apparent in DepEd's policy statements about the objectives and outcomes of the MTBE-MLE reform.

Hornberger (2002) explained that MTB-MLE is opening at the national level in the Philippines through the support of Dep. Ed. and Congress. However, less attention has been given to the perspectives of those at the community level where implementation will occur.

According to Fullan (2003) and Shohamy (2006), the teachers and the parents are the two key stakeholder groups that are often forgotten in the policy process despite holding much power in carrying out a reform. The researcher believed that teachers' problems in teaching mother tongue-based multilingual education influence the academic performance of elementary pupils; hence, this study.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design. This descriptive correlational research aimed to determine the problems and issues in teaching mother tongue based-multi lingual education and pupils' academic performance during the first grading period in the District of Dingle for the school year 2014 - 2015. Personal factors such as age, length of teaching experience, teaching position, and educational qualification were the antecedent variables, the teacher's problems in teaching mother tongue-based multilingual education was the independent variable, and the pupils' academic performance was the dependent variable.

Respondents. The study's respondents were the 33 teachers representing the entire population of grade two teachers in the whole District of Dingle. The participants were classified according to age, length of teaching experience, teaching position, and educational attainment. Of the total respondents, 19 (57.60%) teachers are below 40 years old, and 14 (42.40%) are 41 years old and above. For the category of the length of teaching experience, 21 (63.60%) teachers belong to "short" or below 20 years of teaching experience, and 12 (36.40%) teachers belong to "long" or 20 years and above in teaching experience. For the teaching position, there are 12 (36.40%) teachers who are Teacher I, 7 (21.20%) teachers are Teacher II, and 14 (42.40%) teachers are Teacher III. Finally, for educational attainment, there are 9 (30.30%) teachers who are Bachelor's Degrees, 23 (66.70%) teachers with Bachelor's Degrees with MA Units, and only 1 (3%) teacher who is Master's Degree.

Data Collection Procedure. Permission to conduct the study was secured from the school administrators in the District of Dingle. Letters asking permission to conduct the study and use their teachers as respondents were sent to the District Supervisors, the principals and school heads involved, and the teacher-respondents themselves. The researchers personally administered the questionnaires to the respondents. After filling out the questionnaire, they were gathered, tabulated, interpreted, and analyzed using appropriate descriptive and inferential statistic tools.

Data Analysis Procedure. The gathered data was subjected to the following statistical procedures: The *Frequency Count* was used to determine the number of participants belonging to a class or category of the independent variables. The *Percentage Distribution* was used to determine the proportion of the independent variables' participants belonging to a class or category. The *mean* was used to indicate the levels of the participants' problems encountered in teaching the mother tongue-based multilingual education and the academic performances of their pupils. The *Standard Deviation* was used to determine the homogeneity or heterogeneity of the participants' level of teaching mother tongue-based multilingual education and degree of academic performance. The *Mann-Whitney Test* was used to determine the significant differences in the data between two categories of the independent variables such as age: with age bracket of below 40 years old and 41 years old and above, and the length of teaching experience: categorized as short (below 20 years) and long (20 years old and above). The *Kruskal-Wallis Test* was used to determine the significant differences in the data between three or more categories of the independent variables such as teaching position: categorized as Teacher I, Teacher II, and Teacher III, and educational attainment: classified as bachelor's degree, bachelor's degree with Master of Arts units and master's degree. Lastly, Spearman's rho was used to determine the significance of the relationship between respondents' level of problems and issues in teaching mother tongue-based multilingual education and the academic performance of their pupils.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Problems and Issues in Teaching Mother Tongue-Based-Multilingual Education

Table 1 shows that, as an entire group, the respondents have 'serious' problems and issues ($M = 2.05$; $SD = 0.22$) in teaching mother tongue-based multilingual education (MTB-MLE). Likewise, the respondents in all the categories of the antecedent variables had 'serious' problems and issues in teaching the MTB-MLE. The respondents in the below 40 years category of age had a mean of 2.08 ($SD=0.21$); those in the 41 years old and above category have a mean of 2.01 ($SD=0.23$). When the respondents were classified according to the categories of length of teaching experience, the table shows that those who have 'short' teaching experiences had a mean of 2.02 ($SD= 0.21$), while those who have 'long' teaching experiences had a mean of 2.09 ($SD=0.23$). Meanwhile, the Teacher I respondents had a mean of 2.05 ($SD=0.20$), the Teacher II respondents had a median of 2.15 ($SD=0.24$), and the Teacher III respondents had a mean of 2.00 ($SD=0.22$). Finally, when the respondents were classified according to educational attainment, the table shows that the Bachelor's Degree holders have a mean of 2.00 ($SD= 0.20$), and the Bachelor' Degree holders with MA Units have a mean of 2.08($SD=0.23$). In contrast, the Master's Degree holder has a mean of 2.00.

Table 1. The Levels of the Problems and Issues in Teaching MTB-MLE among the Respondents

Compared Groups	Mean	Description	SD
Entire Group	2.05	Serious	0.22
Age			
Below 40 yrs	2.08	Serious	0.21
41 yrs and above	2.01	Serious	0.23
Length of Teaching Experience			
Short (below 20 yrs)	2.02	Serious	0.21
Long (20 yrs and above)	2.09	Serious	0.23
Teaching Position			
Teacher I	2.05	Serious	0.20
Teacher II	2.15	Serious	0.24
Teacher III	2.00	Serious	0.22
Educational Qualification			
Bachelor's Degree	2.00	Serious	0.20
Bachelor's with MA Units	2.08	Serious	0.23
Master's Degree	2.00	Serious	

The Academic Performance of the Respondents' Pupils

Table 2 showed that, as an entire group, the academic performance of the respondents' pupils is "approaching proficiency" ($M = 80.67$; $SD = 2.53$). When the respondents were classified as to age, the table showed that the pupils of the respondents who were either below 40 years old ($M=80.93$; $SD=3.15$) or 41 years old and above ($M=80.31$; $SD=1.32$) had "approaching proficiency" academic performances. Likewise, the pupils of both the teachers who had 'short' teaching experiences ($M = 80.85$; $SD= 2.69$) and those who had 'long' teaching experiences ($M= 80.35$; $SD=2.29$) had "approaching proficiency" academic performances. Meanwhile, when the pupils were classified according to their teachers' teaching positions, the results showed that the pupils of the Teacher I respondents ($M= 80.21$; $SD= 1.91$), those of the Teacher II respondents ($M= 80.27$; $SD= 2.95$), as well as those of the Teacher III respondents ($M= 81.27$; $SD= 2.82$) exhibited 'approaching proficiency' academic performances. On the other hand, when the pupils were grouped according to their teachers' educational attainment, the table showed the pupils whose teachers were bachelor's degree holders ($M= 79.98$; $SD= 3.67$) and those whose teachers were master's degree holders ($M = 79.80$) had 'developing' academic performances, while those whose teachers have bachelor's degrees with MA units ($M = 81.02$; $SD = 1.89$) had an "approaching proficiency" academic performance.

Table 2. The Academic Performances of the Respondents' Pupils

Compared Groups	Mean	Description	SD
Entire Group	80.67	Approaching Proficiency	2.53
Age			
Below 40 yrs	80.93	Approaching Proficiency	3.15
40 yrs old & above	80.31	Approaching Proficiency	1.32
Length of Teaching Experience			
Short (below 20 yrs)	80.85	Approaching Proficiency	2.69
Long (20 yrs and above)	80.35	Approaching Proficiency	2.29
Teaching Position			
Teacher, I	80.21	Approaching Proficiency	1.91
Teacher II	80.27	Approaching Proficiency	2.95
Teacher III	81.27	Approaching Proficiency	2.82
Educational Attainment			
Bachelor's degree	79.98	Developing	3.67
Bachelor's w/ MA Units	81.02	Approaching Proficiency	1.89
Master's degree	79.80	Developing	–

The Differences in the Levels of the Problems and Issues in Teaching the MTB-MLE among the Respondents Classified according to Age and Length of Teaching Experience

The Mann-Whitney test results in Table 3 revealed non-significant differences in the levels of the problems and issues encountered by the respondents classified as age. ($z = -1.061$; $p = 0.289$) and length of teaching experience ($z = -0.865$; $p = 0.387$). The p-values were greater than 0.05.

This means that, regardless of their age and length of service differences, the respondents had the same levels of problems and issues encountered in teaching the MTB-MLE.

The null hypotheses were accepted, assuming non-significant differences in the levels of problems encountered in teaching the MTB-MLE by the respondents classified according to age and length of teaching experience.

Table 3. The Mann-Whitney Test Results for the Differences in the Levels of the Problems and Issues Encountered in the MTB-MLE by the Respondents Classified according to Age and Length of Teaching Experience

Compared Category	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	z	sig. (2-tailed)
Age				1.0610	.289
Below 40 yrs	19	18.53	352.00		
41 yrs old & above	14	14.93	209.00		
Total	33				
Length of Teaching Experience				0.865	0.387
Short (below 20 yrs)	21	15.90	334.00		
Long (20 yrs & above)	12	18.92	227.00		
Total	33				

The Differences in the Levels of the Problems and Issues in Teaching the MTB-MLE among the Respondents Classified according to Teaching Position and Educational Attainment

The Kruskal-Wallis test results in Table 4 revealed non-significant differences in the levels of the problems and issues encountered by the respondents classified as to teaching position [$\chi^2 (2) = 2.22$; $p = 0.33$] and educational attainment [$\chi^2 (2) = 1.29$; $p = 0.53$]. The p-values were more significant than 0.05.

This means that, regardless of their differences in teaching positions and educational attainment, the respondents had the same problems and issues encountered in teaching the MTB-MLE.

The null hypotheses assuming non-significant differences in the levels of problems encountered in teaching the MTB-MLE by the respondents classified according to teaching position and educational attainment were not rejected.

Table 4. The Kruskal-Wallis Test Results for the Differences in the Levels of the Problems and Issues Encountered in the MTB-MLE by the Respondents Classified according to Teaching Position and Educational Attainment

Compared Category	N	Mean Rank	Chi-Square	df	sig. (2-tailed)
Teaching Position				2	0.33
Teacher I	12	17.00	2.22		
Teacher II	7	21.43			
Teacher III	14	14.79			
Total	33				
Educational Attainment				2	0.53
Bachelor's degree	10	14.40	1.29		
Bachelor's w/MA units	22	18.34			
Master's degree	1	13.50			
Total	33				

The Differences in the Academic Performances of the Respondents' Pupils

The Mann-Whitney test results in Table 5 revealed non-significant differences in the academic performances of the pupils of the respondents classified as to age ($z = -0.619$; $p = 0.536$) and length of teaching experience ($z = -0.187$; $p = 0.852$). The p-values were more significant than 0.05.

This means that, regardless of the differences in age and the length of service of the respondents, their pupils had statistically the same academic performances.

The null hypotheses assuming non-significant differences in the academic performances of the pupils of the respondents classified according to age and length of teaching experience, were accepted.

Table 5. The Mann-Whitney Test Results for the Differences in the Academic Performances of the Pupils of the Respondents Classified according to Age and Length of Teaching Experience

Category	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	z	sig. (2-tailed)
Age				0.619	0.536
Below 40 yrs	19	17.89	340.00		
41 yrs old & above	14	15.79	221.00		
Total	33				
Length of Teaching Experience				0.187	0.852
Short (below 20 yrs)	21	17.24	362.00		
Long (20 yrs & above)	12	16.58	199.00		
Total	33				

The Differences in the Academic Performances of the Pupils of the Respondents Classified according to Teaching Position and Educational Attainment

The Kruskal-Wallis test results in Table 6 revealed non-significant differences in the academic performances of the pupils of the respondents classified as to teaching position [$\chi^2 (2) = 0.30$; $p = 0.86$] and educational attainment [$\chi^2 (2) = 2.697$; $p = 0.260$]. The p-values were more significant than 0.05. The null hypotheses assuming non-significant differences in the academic performances of the pupils of the respondents classified according to a teaching position and educational attainment, were accepted.

This means that, regardless of the differences in teaching positions and the respondents' educational attainment, their pupils had statistically the same academic performances.

Table 6. The Kruskal-Wallis Test Results for the Differences in the Academic Performances of the Pupils of the Respondents Classified according to Teaching Position and Educational Attainment

Compared Groups	N	Mean Rank	Chi-Square	df	sig. (2-tailed)
Teaching Position			0.30	2	0.86
Teacher I	12	16.17			
Teacher II	7	16.29			
Teacher III	14	18.07			
Total	33				
Educational Attainment			2.697	2	0.260
Bachelor's degree	10	14.40			
Bachelor's w/MA units	22	18.95			
Master's degree	1	13.00			
Total	33				

The Relationship between the Respondents' Level of Problems and Issues in Teaching the MTB-MLE and their Pupils' Academic Performances

The Spearman's rho result in Table 7 revealed a non-significant relationship ($r=0.201$; $p=0.262$) between the level of problems and issues encountered in teaching the MTB-MLE by the respondents and the academic performances of their pupils. The p-value was more significant than 0.05. The null hypothesis, which does not assume a significant relationship between these two variables thus not rejected.

This means that the academic performances of their pupils were separate from the level of the problems and issues encountered by the respondents in teaching the MTB-MLE.

Table 7. The Spearman's Rho Result for the Relationship between the Respondents' Level of Problems and Issues in Teaching the MTB-MLE and their Pupils' Academic Performances

Correlated Variables		Problems & Issues	Academic Performance
Problems and Issues	r	1.000	0.201
Sig. (2-tailed)		0.262	
N		33	33
Academic performance	r	0.201	1.000
Sig. (2-tailed)		0.262	
N		33	33

CONCLUSION

When classified as age, length of teaching experience, teaching position, and educational attainment, the entire group had severe problems and issues in teaching MTB-MLE. It means that great attention is needed for this seriousness.

In the categories of age, length of teaching experience, teaching position, and bachelor's degree with MA units, their pupils had approaching proficiency academic performance, and those who are bachelor's degrees pupils had developing performance. The higher the educational attainment of the teacher, the higher the performance of their pupils.

The respondents' differences in age, length of teaching experience, teaching position, and educational attainment do not significantly influence how serious their problems and issues are in teaching the MTB-MLE.

The differences in the respondents' age, length of teaching experience, teaching position, and educational attainment do not significantly influence their pupils' academic performances.

The seriousness of the problems encountered by the respondents in teaching the MTB-MLE has no connection to the academic performances of their pupils.

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